

DAMAGE INITIATION IN A WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITE

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Summary: Over the past several years, new developments in the methodology for predicting ultimate failure of laminated fiber-reinforced plastic (FRP) materials have emerged. While many of these new approaches have been helped by significantly improved computational power, the overall trend appears to be towards predicting failure in materials at the micro (fiber and matrix) rather than the macro (lamina or laminate)-level. A recently developed micro-level approach, Multicontinuum Theory (MCT), was used herein to predict and analyze the onset of damage and ultimate failure of biaxially loaded composite cruciform test specimens. Damage in a composite material typically begins at the constituent level and may, in fact, be limited to only one constituent in some situations. An accurate prediction of constituent failure at sampling points throughout the laminate provides a genesis for progressively analyzing damage propagation in a composite specimen allowing identification of intermediate damage modes. Multicontinuum Theory is a micromechanics based theory and associated numerical algorithm for extracting, virtually without a time penalty, the stress and strain fields for a composites' constituents during a routine structural finite element analysis. A constituent-based, quadratic, stress-interactive, failure criterion was used to take advantage of the micro-scale information provided by MCT. A fully three-dimensional finite element implementation of MCT was used to generate two-dimensional failure envelopes for comparison against experimentally generated data. Experimental two-dimensional failure envelopes were generated by performing biaxial tests on thickness-tapered cruciform specimens. More specifically, a thickness-tapered cruciform specimen has been developed and shown to be capable of producing acceptable results for specific laminate configurations. All biaxial tests were performed utilizing a triaxial testing facility located at the Air Force Research Laboratory, Space Vehicles Directorate. This electromechanical test facility was developed specifically to evaluate the biaxial (in-plane) and triaxial (three-dimensional) response of composite materials. This experimental test facility is capable of generating any combination of tensile or compressive stresses in $\sigma_1:\sigma_2:\sigma_3$ stress space. To date, biaxial tests and numerical predictions have been performed on two cross-ply carbon/epoxy material systems, cross-ply and quasi-isotropic E-Glass/vinyl ester laminates. A complete discussion of the ability of thickness-tapered cruciform specimens to accurately evaluate the biaxial strength of fiber-reinforced composites will be presented, as will the correlation between MCT numerical predictions and experimental results.

Keywords: woven, fabric, multicontinuum, biaxial, failure

INTRODUCTION

There has been an increasing use of textile type "fabrics" as reinforcement in composite materials. A woven fabric is composed of fiber bundles referred to as "rovings" or if the fiber bundles are twisted about their longitudinal axis they are termed "yarns". The number of individual fibers or "ends" making up a fiber bundle can be varied as well as the fiber diameter which increases the diameter of the roving and the overall thickness of the weave. Bulk weave reinforcement comes off textile type looms in near continuous lengths and relatively narrow widths (approximately 1 meter). Fiber bundles that have their

longitudinal axis parallel to the length dimension are termed “warp” rovings. Fiber bundles with their longitudinal axis parallel to the width dimension are termed “fill” or “weft” rovings. The rovings can be interlaced in many patterns but for clarity we will focus on a simple weave pattern. Known as a “plain weave”, fill rovings alternately travel over and under the orthogonal warp roving in an undulating manner as shown in Figure 1. Symmetry of the plain weave allows a relative small region, the Representative Volume Element (RVE), to be used to describe the periodicity of the weave structure. The speed of the weaving operation is in large part determined by the placement of the fill rovings which are actually woven about the warp rovings. Weavers have determined that they can use less fill than warp rovings per unit length (approximately 5 warp to 4 fill) and speed up the manufacturing process without significantly reducing the reinforcement effect in the width direction relative to the length direction. If the ratio of warp to fill rovings is 1:1, the plain weave is called “balanced”, if not the plain weave is called “unbalanced”. Ply angles within laminates made from woven fabrics are referenced to the axis of the warp rovings.

Figure 1 Plain weave fabric with RVE shown.

Woven roving “preforms” have two distinct advantages over conventional unidirectional fiber reinforcement. The first is near identical strength and stiffness in orthogonal directions within a single ply which is a significant consideration for multiaxial loading situations. The second is the thickness of the weave perform can be varied. Thick, orthogonally reinforced laminates can be achieved faster using weaves which is appealing to composite fabricators. For example, to achieve a laminate with quasi-isotropic in-plane material properties using a weave requires only four fiber placement operations to put down the $[0/45_2/0]$ plys whereas it would require eight fiber placement operations with conventional unidirectional fibers, $[0/90/+45/-45/-45/+45/90/0]$.

There are also two major disadvantages of woven reinforced composites. There is a significantly increased complexity in the mechanics of ply failure due to interaction between the warp and fill rovings and the addition of a third dimension component due to roving undulation. Quantifying the advantage of simultaneous orthogonal reinforcement becomes a disadvantage because it requires multiaxial testing capability which is, arguably, an order of magnitude more difficult than uniaxial testing. In this paper we attempt to address these difficulties by: 1) Using a constituent based failure analysis methodology to investigate the complex damage mechanisms inherent in woven fabric composites. 2) Using a multiaxial test frame to generate a two-dimensional failure envelope for laminates made from woven fabrics.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE

Multicontinuum Theory (MCT) [1,2,3] is a highly efficient combination of micromechanics and the classic strain decomposition approach of Hill [4]. MCT extracts the constituent strain/stresses fields from those of the composite they form. Constituent stresses are then used as inputs to a quadratic stress-interactive constituent based failure criteria[1]. This allows MCT to efficiently track damage progression from constituent failure at the micro scale to composite failure at the macro scale. MCT begins with a natural extension of a single continuum theory, i.e., treating a heterogeneous material with two clearly identifiable phases as a multicontinuum where each individual phase is allowed to retain its identity. MCT extends the volume average single continuum definition of stress, Eqn (1), to the constituent level as Eqns (2) and (3). For example, in the continuum point of Figure 2, the volume averaged stresses for the composite domain, fiber domain ($\alpha = f$) and matrix domain ($\beta = m$) may be expressed as:

Figure 2 Continuum point for a two constituent heterogeneous material.

$$\underline{\sigma} = \frac{1}{V} \int_D \underline{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) dV \quad (1)$$

$$\underline{\sigma}_\alpha = \frac{1}{V_\alpha} \int_{D_\alpha} \underline{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) dV, \quad (2)$$

$$\underline{\sigma}_\beta = \frac{1}{V_\beta} \int_{D_\beta} \underline{\sigma}(\mathbf{x}) dV, \quad (3)$$

where, $D = D_\alpha \cup D_\beta$.

Let the composite and constituent stress fields be defined by Eqns (1)-(3). Combining these equations, with V_α and V_β designating the fiber and matrix volume fractions respectively, leads directly to

$$\underline{\sigma} = V_\alpha \underline{\sigma}_\alpha + V_\beta \underline{\sigma}_\beta, \quad (4a) \quad \underline{\varepsilon} = V_\alpha \underline{\varepsilon}_\alpha + V_\beta \underline{\varepsilon}_\beta. \quad (4b)$$

Again, it is emphasized that the averaging process that results in these equations. That is, it was decided to not be concerned with stress and strain variations through individual constituents at the microscopic level, but only with their phase averaged values. This is an information compromise that separates structural analysis from micromechanical analysis. Accounting for stress variations throughout individual volumes of reinforcement and their surrounding matrix material, even in a modest structure, is simply not possible or desirable.

Finite element solutions of structural problems produce stress and strain fields of the composite, thereby providing two of the four unknowns in Eqns (4) and (5). To provide closure of the equations, constitutive relations are required for the composite as well as the constituents. Assuming elastic behavior for the composite and constituents there follows:

$$\{\sigma_\delta\} = [C_\delta] (\{\varepsilon_\delta\} - \{\varepsilon_{\delta 0}\}), \quad \text{where,} \quad \{\varepsilon_{\delta 0}\} = T \{\eta_\delta\}. \quad (5)$$

$[C_\delta]$ represent material stiffness matrices and $\{\varepsilon_{\delta 0}\}$ represent the thermal strains for $\delta = \alpha, \beta$, or no subscript (composite). $\{\eta_\delta\}$ represents the coefficients of thermal expansion and T the relative temperature. Eqns (4)-(5) can be combined to yield an expression for the constituent strain $\{\varepsilon_m\}$ as a function of the composite strain,

$$\{\varepsilon_\beta\} = (V_\beta [1] + V_\alpha [A])^{-1} (\{\varepsilon\} - \theta \{\eta\}), \quad (6)$$

where, $[A] = -\frac{V_\beta}{V_\alpha} ([C] - [C_\alpha])^{-1} ([C] - [C_\beta])$, $[1] = \text{Identity matrix}$,

$$\{a\} = ([C] - [C_\alpha])^{-1} ([C]\{\alpha\} - V_\alpha [C_\alpha]\{\alpha_\alpha\} - V_\beta [C_\beta]\{\alpha_\beta\}).$$

Typically $[C_\delta]$ and $\{\alpha_\delta\}$ are assumed known constituent material properties. The composite terms, $[C]$ and $\{\eta\}$, can be developed from micromechanical modeling using the constituent values as input [3]. Substituting Eqn (6) back into (4) yields an expression for $\{\varepsilon_\alpha\}$,

$$\{\varepsilon_\alpha\} = \frac{1}{V_\alpha} (\{\varepsilon\} - V_\beta \{\varepsilon_\beta\}). \quad (7)$$

Eqns (6) and (7) allow phase averaged constituent strains to be calculated from composite strains at any point. Using Eqn (5) constituent stresses can be calculated.

In the case of a heterogeneous material with three clearly identifiable phases, α, β , and γ , the two constituent development can be extended by initially combining two of the constituents analytically, α

and β to form the constituent $\alpha\beta$ and use Eqns (6) and (7) to determine constituent values for $\alpha\beta$ and γ . Equations (6) and (7) can then be recursively applied to determine constituent values for α , β , by considering $\alpha\beta$ a two constituent composite [2]. Both the two and three constituent MCT models have been implemented within a finite element program [5].

Constituent stresses supply the input to a quadratic stress-interactive failure criteria [5] of the form:

$$A_1 I_1 + B_1 I_1^2 + A_2 I_2 + B_2 I_2^2 + C_{12} I_1 I_2 + A_3 I_3 + A_4 I_4 = 1, \quad (8)$$

where I_i , $i = 1, 4$, are the transversely isotropic stress invariants and A_i , B_i , C_{ij} , are the experimentally derived failure parameters.

Development of both a two and three constituent MCT model is driven by the type of analysis needed. For a conventional composite made from uniaxial lamina, two constituents are clearly identifiable, fiber and matrix, hence the two constituent model is applicable. For composites with woven fabric reinforcement, the number of constituent that can be identified is dependent on the scale used to view the material. At a relatively low and narrow field of view, only two constituents are identifiable, fiber and matrix, which are used to create a complex three dimensional weave structure. At a higher and wider field of view, three constituents are clearly identifiable, warp roving, fill roving, and matrix.

Two failure states were assumed for the two constituent model: 1) fiber and 2) matrix. Four major constituent failure states were assumed in the three constituent model: 1) warp roving transversely (matrix failure within the roving), 2) warp roving longitudinally (fiber failure within the roving), 3) fill roving transversely, 4) fill roving longitudinally. Clearly the constituent stresses and strains developed previously are based on average values. The concept of average values at a continuum point applies to material properties also, i.e., there is no variation across the point in either constituent. Therefore, when a constituent material fails, it does so absolutely without directionality and only the other constituent remains at that point. Failure of a constituent during a finite element analysis is simply a change in material properties. The “new” material replacing the failed constituent properties result in essentially zero stiffness and strength, hence there are no computations required to define new constituent properties and the resulting damaged composite properties can be calculated before any analysis which significantly increased analytical efficiency.

To illustrate the appropriate use of the a two or three constituent MCT model one must first consider the RVE of a plain weave as shown in Figure 3. To simulate the behavior of the RVE with the two constituent model requires approximately 1500 hexagonal elements. This provides a high resolution analytical window on the behavior of the fiber and matrix constituents that make up the weave structure. However, to generate a 2-D failure envelop in $\sigma_x:\sigma_y$ stress space would require on the order of fifty separate runs with each run requiring approximately one *hour* on an Windows/Intel computer. To simulate the behavior of the RVE with the three constituent model requires a *single* element. While some analytical resolution is lost, each run necessary to generate a 2-D failure envelop takes on the order of one *minute*.

Figure 3 Micromechanics model of a RVE for a plain weave fabric[2]. Three quarters of the top layer of matrix have been removed for clarity.

Once the laminates were identified that were to be tested in the present study, 5 uniaxial tensile tests were performed on each laminate configuration. Under uniaxial loading fabric reinforced laminates are known to exhibit a knee in their tensile stress-strain curve [6] where the overall stiffness shows a distinct shift between an initial (pre-knee) and final (post-knee) region as shown in Figure 4 along with two and three constituent MCT simulations of a similarly loaded RVE. Experimental data showed an average stiffness reduction of 22% between initial and final modulus values for a $[0/90]_s$ (cross-ply) laminate. A 29% average reduction occurred in a $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ (quasi-isotropic) laminate.

Figure 4 Uniaxial tension response of a plain weave E-glass/vinyl ester cross-ply laminate.

It was noted that significant nonlinear behavior occurred within both the pre- and post-knee regions. Therefore, the two constituent model was used for high resolution examination of the failure progression in the RVE under uniaxial tension.

As can be shown in the Figure sequence 5a, b, c, d, e, and f, non-catastrophic composite damage begins at 120 MPa, very early in the load history. Preliminary examination of the analysis indicates that matrix failure initiates at the “flat” section of the fill rovings and not in the undulation region where a combined tensile-shear stress state exist. Matrix damage initiates in the warps at 160 MPa. Fiber failure in the warps initiates immediately thereafter at 170 MPa and does not initiate at the undulation boundary of the warp rovings. Whether this is an artifact of the finite element model or an accurate representation of weave architecture remains to be determined. Fiber failure occurs through the warp thickness but not completely across the width at 360 MPa so the RVE continues to load. Complete matrix failure in the fills and fiber failure through the warp thickness and across the warp width results in catastrophic rupture of the RVE at approximately 380 MPa.

Figure 5 Progressive failure of the weave RVE under uniaxial tension. From left to right and top to bottom: a) 110 MPa b) 120 MPa c) 160 MPa d) 170 MPa e) 250 MPa f) 360 MPa. The RVE failed at 380 MPa. Note blue = undamaged composite, green = damaged due to matrix failure, red = damage due to fiber failure.

The three constituent MCT model was used to efficiently generate the analytical final failure envelope by conducting biaxial load simulations. The laminate was loaded in a step-wise manner with constant x-direction/y-direction stress ratios analogous to the experimental stress ratios discussed in the next section.

Final failure in the progressive, nonlinear analysis was deemed to occur in the simulation when the laminate could no longer sustain the load at a particular step in the load history and displacements grew without bound.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Experimentally, a two-dimensional failure envelope was generated by performing biaxial tests on thickness-tapered cruciform specimens fabricated from an 18-oz biased (5 warp/4 fill rovings) plain weave E-glass/vinyl ester laminate with warp rovings oriented in $[0/90]_s$ (cross-ply) configuration. A total of 29 biaxial tests were performed on the cross-ply laminate in all quadrants of $\sigma_1:\sigma_2$ stress space. Seven biaxial tests were performed on a $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ (quasi-isotropic) fabric reinforced laminate configuration to determine if a laminate of this construction could be successfully tested using a thickness-tapered cruciform specimen. All biaxial tests were performed utilizing the triaxial testing facility shown in Figure 6. This electromechanical test facility was developed specifically to evaluate the biaxial (in-plane) and triaxial (three-dimensional) response of composite materials. This experimental test facility is capable of generating any combination of tensile or compressive stresses in $\sigma_1:\sigma_2:\sigma_3$ stress space[7,8].

Figure 6 Photograph of triaxial test facility.

A specific thickness-tapered cruciform biaxial test specimen geometry, as shown in Figure 7, used in the present study was determined through a combination of experience gained by the authors in previous studies and expected ultimate strength values of the E-glass/vinyl ester laminates tested [7,9,10]. Because cruciform-shaped specimens have two intersecting loading directions, there exists the possibility of load sharing between adjacent loading arms. That is, it is possible that all of the applied load in one direction may not be directed into the gage section, leading to inaccurate stress level predictions in the biaxially loaded gage section. Fortunately, it is possible, but not trivial, to quantify the levels of load sharing for each material system and specimen geometry. Referred to as the bypass correction factor[7,8], this value gives an indication of the amount of applied force that bypasses the thickness-tapered gage section. The specific bypass ratios used in the present study were found to be between 1.3 and 1.55 for the cross-ply and 1.67 for the quasi-isotropic laminates.

Once each thickness-tapered cruciform specimen was CNC machined, the procedure for generating ultimate biaxial strength values began by loading each specimen at a rate of 1.27 mm/min while maintaining the appropriate stress ratio until ultimate specimen failure occurred. Each test was performed in load control by maintaining a ratio of applied stress in the global x-direction (drive axis) to the applied stress in the global y-direction (slave axis). The notation used to identify the particular stress ratio is, x-direction magnitude/y-direction magnitude, with a positive sign indicating tensile and a negative sign indicating compressive values. For example, a stress ratio of 1/-2 denotes a test in which the magnitude of the compressive stress applied in the y-direction is twice that of the tensile stress applied in the x-direction. The stress ratios performed in the present study for the cross-ply laminate were 1/1, 2/1, 1/0, 2/-1, 1/-1, 1/-2, -1/0, -1/-2, and -1/-1. A minimum of three tests were performed for each

Figure 7 Thickness-tapered cruciform specimen. All dimensions in mm.

stress ratio for the cross-ply laminate. For the quasi-isotropic laminate, stress ratios of 1/1, 1/0, 1/-1, and -1/-1 were investigated. Finally, the measured biaxial strength of each specimen was corrected using the bypass correction factor to determine the ultimate biaxial strengths that were used to verify the numerical predictions in the present study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 8 presents both the experimental and analytical biaxial failure envelope for a cross-ply laminate. The failure envelope generated by the three constituent MCT model is in close agreement with the experimentally determined data. Material and loading symmetry reduced the number of data points required to generate a full $\sigma_1:\sigma_2$ failure envelope in half. Both the experimental and analytical data were generated in all of quadrant IV, the lower halves of stress quadrants I and III, and then mirrored across the axis of symmetry. The authors believe that the close agreement between the MCT predictions and the experimental data lend credibility to both the numerical and experimental techniques used in the present study. Especially in view of the complexity of the nonlinear failure mechanics of woven reinforcement and the variation inherent in the significant number of parameters, e.g., material constants, laminate geometry, specimen geometry, testing variables, etc., that have the potential to cause errors.

Figure 8 Three constituent MCT predicted failure envelope and experimental data for an 18-oz biased (5 warp/4 fill rovings) plain weave E-glass/vinyl ester cross-ply $[0/90]_s$ laminate.

The objectives for testing the quasi-isotropic laminate was to explore the feasibility of testing cruciform specimens taken from this laminate architecture and not to generate a complete numerical and experimental failure envelope in $\sigma_1:\sigma_2$ stress space. Figure 9 presents the predicted failure envelope and experimental data for the quasi-isotropic laminate tested. The limited number of biaxial tests performed on the quasi-isotropic laminate precludes significant analysis of the results. However, preliminary data, such as failures in the gage section, repeatable biaxial strengths and good correlation with MCT predictions in quadrants I and III, indicate that these tests can be performed successfully using the techniques and cruciform specimens described in the previous section. However there is a puzzling lack of correlation between analytical model and experimental data in quadrants II and IV. This clearly indicates inaccuracies in either the experimental data or numerical predictions or both.

Figure 9 Three constituent MCT predicted failure envelope and experimental data for an 18-oz biased (5 warp/4 fill rovings) plain weave E-glass/vinyl ester quasi-isotropic $[0/90/\pm 45]_s$ laminate.

Additionally, the bypass correction factor used for the biaxial quasi-isotropic data presented herein was 1.67. This means that 2/5 of the applied force in one loading direction is bypassing the gage section of the specimen. While the authors are concerned with the validity of a bypass value this high, it is not totally unexpected when testing a quasi-isotropic laminate configuration. The $\pm 45^\circ$ plies in a quasi-isotropic laminate provide an avenue for force to bypass the gage section that cannot be altered. In an attempt to validate the magnitude of the bypass ratio, conventional finite element analysis was used to numerically determine the bypass correction factor for both laminates test configuration, Figure 10. Preliminary numerical analysis determined bypass correction factors that were within 5% of the experimentally determined values. The authors believe that while the bypass effect is undesirable, it has been, in the cross-ply case, and can be, in the quasi-isotropic case, overcome by thoughtful experimental methods. Again, the preliminary nature of these results is stressed and the authors acknowledge that both the analytical and experimental methods warrant further investigation and development.

Figure 10 Finite element analysis model of the thick-tapered cruciform specimen (1/8th model due to three planes of symmetry).

CONCLUSIONS

The favorable and complementary failure surfaces obtained in the present study are preliminary verification for the techniques used to determine the biaxial strength of composite laminates. The authors believe that the biaxial failure envelope for the cross-ply laminate generated herein represents a reasonable approximation of laminate strength throughout the entire two-dimensional $\sigma_1:\sigma_2$ stress space for this material. Results for the quasi-isotropic laminate shows that there is still much work to be done. The authors intend to continued the development of the techniques used in the present study. This will ensure that much-needed experimental biaxial data on this and other materials will be generated and made available to the composites community.

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